

The mean temperature follows the development of the Earth's Energy Imbalance and contains a quadratic term in its time dependence.

The decrease in Earth's albedo has become the dominant driver of rising mean temperature.

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Research paper on the relationship between the development of the Earth's Energy Imbalance and the mean temperature (GSAT)

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Abstract

The extreme rise in the Global Surface Average Temperature (GSAT) during the years 2023–2024 sparked a lively debate as to whether this represented a new trend or merely a random cluster of extreme values. In this publication, using measurement data from NASA's CERES programme (covering the period 2000–2025), it is demonstrated that the temperature trend is not linear but necessarily includes a quadratic term.

This is a consequence of the increasing proportion of self-reinforcing cycles associated with changes in the Earth's albedo. During the period under study, the decrease in the Earth's albedo was the dominant driver of the temperature rise, with a radiative forcing (RF) value of 2.38 W/m^2 . It exceeded the contribution of the radiative forcing caused by the increase in CO_2 concentration (0.77 W/m^2) by more than threefold and is already greater than the CO_2 forcing since the start of the Industrial Revolution (approx. 2.28 W/m^2 by the end of 2025).

A temperature function was derived from the trend in the Earth's Energy Imbalance (EEI) and compared with ERA5 GSAT measurements. It was found that the temperature measurements follow the EEI trend with a 10-month delay. Based on these results, a representative temperature function was determined which accurately reflects the temporal evolution of the climate system. Using this temperature function, the rate of temperature rise was determined to be 0.17°C per decade for the period 2001–2010 and 0.40°C per decade for the period 2015–2024, thereby demonstrating its significant acceleration.

Determining the exceedance of important temperature thresholds using the representative temperature function results in a dramatic reduction in the corresponding timeframes compared to the method of determining CO_2 budgets used to date, which was applied in the IPCC AR6 report. According to this, the 1.5°C threshold was already exceeded in July 2025. The 2°C threshold will be exceeded in mid-2034, whereas, based on the AR6 CO_2 budget (assuming CO_2 emissions remain constant at 2025 levels), this was not expected to occur until the end of 2047. Around this time, the temperature curve will already have reached the 3°C threshold.

These enormous differences are due to the application of a linear relationship between cumulative CO_2 emissions and the rise in GSAT – a relationship that is no longer valid – as well as to the massive underestimation of the feedbacks associated with albedo change in the AR6.

1. Introduction

The rapid rise in Global Average Surface Temperature (GSAT) of more than 1.5°C between 2023 and 2024 has sparked a lively scientific debate as to whether this is merely a temporary, exceptional anomaly (outliers) or a lasting new trend. Some studies have identified a significant acceleration in global warming in recent years, most recently Foster & Rahmstorf [1]. The authors found an acceleration in the rate of temperature rise, depending on the temperature dataset, in the range of 0.35–0.42°C per decade. Some commentaries have pointed out, among other things, that this development lies within the range of current climate models and therefore cannot be described as a significant new trend. There have also been attempts to explain this phenomenon, pointing to the influence of reduced aerosol emissions from shipping; see Hansen et al. [2]. However, it has not yet been possible to fully clarify the cause of the “temperature jump”.

Previous approaches to explaining the rise in temperature have focused almost exclusively on statistical methods and the approximately linear relationship between the GSAT and cumulative anthropogenic CO₂ emissions. This relationship also forms the basis for calculating so-called CO₂ budgets within the framework of the IPCC AR6 report [3], i.e. the remaining emissions still possible for compliance with the Paris targets of 1.5°C and 2°C. It must be pointed out, however, that the assumed linear relationship is not a law of nature and its validity over a longer period of time cannot therefore be taken for granted.

Until now, the climate debate has focused almost exclusively on the effects of greenhouse gases, while the second fundamental mechanism of the climate system – changes in the Earth’s albedo – has received little attention.

Due to the law of conservation of energy, the energy absorbed by the climate system—which can be determined from Earth Energy Imbalance (EEI) values—represents the fundamental parameter. Via the effective heat capacity of the climate system, the absorbed energy must be directly related to the mean temperature. Satellite measurements from NASA’s CERES programme, which are now available for a period of 25 years, offer a unique opportunity to compare the available EEI data with the measured temperature data.

The period from 2000 to 2025 seems rather short compared with the period since the start of the Industrial Revolution around 1850. However, it is important to bear in mind that almost half of anthropogenic global warming has occurred during this period and that very high-quality data is available.

This study examines the relationship between EEI and GSAT. First, the evolution of the EEI and its key components is investigated. Based on the results of this analysis, a temperature curve is derived and compared with measured temperature values. Finally, a representative time-dependent temperature function is determined, which reflects the current temperature evolution of the climate system and can also be used to forecast future developments. In addition, the values for the radiative forcing (RF) of various components are compared over the period under investigation.

2. Methods

2.1 Analysis of CERES data

The study is based on an analysis of data on the Earth's energy balance for the period 2000–2025, compiled as part of NASA's CERES programme (EBAF-TOA dataset – Level 3b) [4]. The analysis used monthly global averages for the period from March 2000 to the end of 2025, from which 12-month moving averages were calculated. The following parameters were used:

- Incoming solar radiation,
- Reflected solar radiation,
- Outgoing longwave radiation (OLR),
- Absorbed solar radiation (ASR), calculated as the difference between the values for incoming solar radiation and reflected solar radiation,
- Albedo, calculated as the ratio of reflected to incoming solar radiation,
- TOA net energy flux (Net Radiation), calculated as the difference between the values for ASR and OLR, hereinafter referred to as Earth Energy Imbalance (EEI).

The relationships between the parameters are shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1 Illustration of how the key parameters are determined as part of NASA's CERES programme. Image credit: Image courtesy of the CERES Science Team at NASA Langley Research Center in Hampton, Virginia, USA

A positive EEI value indicates the rate at which additional heat energy is added to the Earth's climate system and is therefore the key parameter for changes in GSAT. Like all other values used, it is expressed in W/m^2 (an average value calculated across the entire Earth's surface). The development of the EEI is shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2 EEI development (values in W/m^2) from 2000 to 2025, with linear trend lines in phases 1 and 2.

The development of the EEI shows two different phases over the period under review. Up to the end of 2010 (Phase 1), the EEI still occasionally reached a value of 0 (i.e. the absorbed solar radiation was exactly offset by the Earth's long-wave infrared radiation). From 2011 onwards (Phase 2), this no longer occurs; instead, increasingly higher EEI values are recorded. The linear trend in Phase 1 corresponds to an increase of $0.32 W/m^2$ per decade, while in Phase 2 it rises to $0.49 W/m^2$.

The EEI shows the absolute values of the heat absorbed by the climate system, but does not provide any information about the causes of this trend. Further information can be obtained by examining the main components of the EEI – absorbed solar radiation (ASR) and outgoing long-wave infrared radiation (OLR; see Figure 3).

Figure 3 Absorbed solar radiation (ASR) and outgoing long-wave infrared radiation (OLR) with linear trend lines for phases 1 and 2. Values in W/m^2 .

In Figure 3, phases 1 and 2, which were already presented in Figure 2, are even more clearly evident. It should be noted that rising concentrations of greenhouse gases (GHGs) cannot cause an increase in absorbed solar radiation. As solar radiation is nearly constant, the EEI in this case is caused by the suppression of outgoing long-wave infrared radiation. The EEI therefore arises from the downward shift of the OLR curve.

However, an increase in the amount of solar radiation absorbed, given constant solar irradiance, can only be caused by a reduction in the reflection of short-wave solar radiation. This corresponds to a decrease in the Earth's albedo. The two phases are discussed in more detail below.

Phase 1

Until the end of 2010, the amount of solar radiation absorbed rose only moderately, while infrared radiation emitted by the Earth remained largely constant. There were several points in time when the ASR and OLR curves overlapped and the EEI was close to 0. This is an indication that a significant proportion of the EEI is attributable to rising

GHG emissions. However, the change in Earth's albedo responsible for the rise in the absorption curve is already clearly noticeable.

Phase 2

From 2011 onwards, there is a significant increase in absorbed solar radiation (ASR). It is striking that, from this point onwards, there is no longer any overlap with the outgoing longwave radiation (OLR) curve. Although the values for outgoing longwave infrared radiation (OLR) also rise, they do so at only 50% of the rate of the absorption curve. This means that there is a steady increase in the EEI, see Figure 2. The sharp rise in the ASR curve suggests that, during this phase, the change in albedo already accounts for the dominant contribution to the EEI. A more precise estimation of the contributions based on the RF values will be carried out later.

2.2 Albedo decrease as the primary driver of rising temperature

Based on the above, the rise in the EEI is to a large extent attributable to the decrease in Earth's albedo. Its development is presented in Figure 4. In fact, between 2000 and 2025, Earth's albedo fell by 0.70%. Here, too, two distinct phases can be observed. Until the end of 2010, the downward trend was more moderate (-0.16% per decade); from 2011 onwards, the downward trend more than doubled to -0.36% per decade.

Figure 4 Development of Earth albedo 2000–2025 (12-month moving average, values in %) with linear trend lines for phases 1 and 2

The change in albedo is caused by various self-reinforcing feedback loops:

- Reduction of reflective low-lying cloud cover
- Decline in Arctic sea ice
- Decline in snow cover (area and duration)

In the case of the latter two, the increasing frequency of forest fires (soot particles) and the shift from snowfall to rainfall are further accelerating the reduction in albedo. Furthermore, the reduction in the shielding effect of aerosols resulting from air pollution control measures is having an impact on albedo.

A 0.70% reduction in the Earth's albedo may seem small, but in reality it represents a massive shift in the Earth's energy balance. This change is associated with a TOA radiative forcing (RF) of 2.38 W/m². To assess the contribution of GHG emissions to the rise in temperature, the CO₂ forcing must first be determined. This is done using the formula

$$\Delta RF = 5,35 * \ln\left(\frac{c}{c_0}\right)$$

where c_0 denotes the CO₂ concentration at the start of the time interval and c denotes the concentration at the end of the time interval in consideration. Table 1 below shows a comparison of the RF values for the period 2000–2025 for the two phases shown in Figure 4:

<i>Year</i>	<i>CO₂- Concentration</i>	<i>ΔRF CO₂</i>	<i>ΔRF Albedo</i>
2000	369		
2010	389	0,28	0,54
2025	426	0,49	1,84
Total		0,77	2,38

Table 1 Additional forcing (RF) from CO₂ and albedo change for the period 2000–2025, values in W/m². CO₂ concentration in ppm, source: NOAA [5].

As can be seen from Table 1, up until 2010 (Phase 1), the albedo forcing was approximately twice that of CO₂. From 2011 onwards (Phase 2), the albedo component becomes very dominant, reaching almost four times the CO₂ forcing (a factor of 3,78).

Over the entire period under consideration, the additional CO₂ forcing amounts to only a third (32,3%) of the radiative forcing (RF) value associated with the albedo change. The change in Earth's albedo is therefore the dominant forcing component in the period 2000–2025 and is largely responsible for the rise in mean temperature. The forcing caused by the loss of albedo has already exceeded the total CO₂ forcing since the start of the Industrial Revolution (approx. 2.28 W/m² by the end of 2025).

2.3 The relationship between EEI and the energy uptake of the climate system

Since EEI represents the additional heat input to the climate system, its linear increase automatically causes the amount of energy input to the climate system to become a quadratic function of time.

The linear increase in the EEI can be expressed using the following formula:

$$EEI(t) = c \cdot t$$

The constant c indicates the slope of the EEI curve over time.

The EEI value describes the change over time of the energy E_{abs} absorbed by the climate system, which is responsible for the rise in mean temperature:

$$EEI(t) = \frac{dE_{\text{abs}}(t)}{dt}$$

The following relationship describes the time-dependent nature of the amount of energy absorbed:

$$E_{\text{abs}}(t) = \int_0^t EEI(t_1) dt_1 = \int_0^t (c \cdot t_1) dt_1 = \frac{1}{2} c \cdot t^2$$

The amount of energy absorbed by the climate system therefore exhibits a quadratic component of time dependence (parabolic trend). Since the additional energy absorbed via

$$\Delta E_{\text{abs}} = c_w \cdot \Delta T$$

(c_w represents the effective heat capacity of the climate system, assumed to be constant)

is directly related to the change in mean temperature, the temperature function must therefore also contain a quadratic component.

Due to the presence of the quadratic term, the concept of a linear relationship between GSAT and cumulative CO₂ emissions can no longer be upheld. When assessing temperature trends, therefore, rather than using linear regression, the correct curve fit must be performed using a second-degree polynomial (parabola).

2.4 Calculation of the temperature curve from the EEI

Since EEI determines the energy uptake of the climate system, it stands to reason that the trend in mean temperature must follow that of the absorbed energy. This holds true for the trend lines, as temperature fluctuations caused by various phenomena, such as the ENSO cycle (the shift from El Niño to La Niña), can significantly influence individual data points. It should be noted, however, that the mechanisms behind these temperature fluctuations do not cause additional warming, but merely redistribute the energy already stored in the climate system. It is therefore not necessary to take them into account in the context of this study.

First, the amount of energy absorbed by the climate system E_{abs} must be determined. The result is shown in Figure 5. As can be seen, the parabolic trend line closely matches the shape of the absorption curve. The coefficient of determination R^2 is 0.9764.

Figure 5. Energy uptake by the Earth's climate system, derived from the trend in the EEI for the period 2000–2025 (values in ZJ), with a parabolic regression curve (second-degree polynomial).

Accordingly, the climate system absorbed an additional 323 ZJ of energy (1 zettajoule equals 10^{21} joules) during the period under consideration. The wave-like fluctuations in the energy curve shown in the graph are the result of changes in solar radiation over the annual cycle. Due to the eccentricity of the Earth's orbit, the intensity of solar radiation fluctuates by $\pm 3.3\%$ around the annual mean ($1/4$ of the solar constant).

Determination of the effective heat capacity of the climate system

To calculate the temperature curve derived from the EEL, the effective heat capacity c_w of the climate system is required:

$$c_w = \frac{\Delta E_{abs}}{\Delta T}$$

It corresponds to the amount of energy required to raise the average temperature by 1K. The heat capacity is assumed to remain constant over the period under consideration.

In addition to the energy difference, the temperature difference is also required to determine the heat capacity. In this study, the GSAT temperature dataset ERA5 from the Copernicus Climate Change Service (C3S) [6,7] is used (air temperature at a height of 2 m above the surface, global monthly averages for the years 2000 to 2025, relative to the period 1850–1900). The measurement data used are presented in Figure 6 with a second-degree regression curve.

Figure 6 The ERA5 GSAT dataset (2000–2025) used in the study, with a parabolic trend curve. Source: ERA5. Credit: C3S/ECMWF

Due to the already mentioned annual cycle of solar radiation, the amount of energy absorbed by the climate system depends on the choice of end point. To eliminate this influence of the solar cycle, the average value over three annual cycles was used

(starting point March 2000, end points March 2022 to February 2025). The energy values were referenced to the corresponding points on the trend curve of the temperature series.

The value of the heat capacity c_w determined in this way is 445.8 ZJ/K.

Calculation of the temperature derived from the EEI development

Using the determined heat capacity, the temperature T_{EEI} derived from the EEI trend can be calculated:

$$T_{EEI}(t) = \frac{E_{abs}(t)}{c_w}$$

Their progression is shown in Figure 7.

Figure 7 Temperature curve T_{EEI} derived from EEI values, with a parabolic trend line

3. Results

3.1 Determination of the representative temperature function of the climate system T_{CS}

As already explained in section 2.2, the time-dependence of the temperature function includes a quadratic term. Analyses of the GSAT using linear regression cannot therefore provide accurate results. As part of this study, a representative temperature function T_{CS} was determined which accurately reflects past temperature trends and enables reliable forecasts of future trends.

The temperature curve T_{EEI} calculated in 2.3 was used as the basis for determining the temperature function (see Figure 7). Figure 8 shows a comparison of this curve with the measured values from the ERA5 dataset. To adjust the zero point, the offset value was chosen such that the two trend lines coincide at the start of the period under investigation.

Figure 8 Comparison of the calculated temperature T_{EEI} with ERA5 measurements, showing parabolic trend curves

As can be seen from the figure above, the calculated temperature T_{EEI} rises slightly faster than the ERA5 temperature values.

However, it must be kept in mind that the EEI values represent the current heat flux, and that the additional energy is only distributed within the climate system after a delay, enabling it to cause a change in the mean temperature. To determine the magnitude of this time delay, the minimum deviation between the trend lines of the time-shifted temperature curve T_{EEI} and the ERA5 measurement data was calculated. The minimum deviation is achieved with a time shift of 10 months. The corresponding temperature curve is shown in Figure 9.

Figure 9 The temperature curve T_{EEI} , shifted by 10 months, compared with the ERA5 measurements

The trend curve of the time-shifted temperature curve T_{EEI} shown in Figure 9 can therefore be interpreted as a representative temperature function of the climate system T_{CS} :

$$T_{\text{CS}}(t) = 6,27766 \cdot 10^{-9} \cdot t^2 + 1,88701 \cdot 10^{-5} \cdot t + 0,77930573$$

(Units of the time variable t : number of days from 1 January 2000)

This temperature function T_{cs} provides an optimal description of the evolution of the GSAT between 2000 and 2025 and can be used both to determine the rise in temperature and as a reference scenario for analyses of future trends in average temperature. It remains valid as long as there are no significant changes in GHG emissions. In recent years, despite the targets set out in the Paris Agreement, emissions have continued to rise moderately rather than falling as required. Assuming constant emissions in the coming years therefore represents an optimistic scenario from today's perspective.

In result, it can be stated that the development of the mean temperature could be reconstructed very accurately from the physical parameters measured as part of the CERES programme. It is a second-degree polynomial function (a parabola).

Considering the findings outlined above, the linear relationship between mean temperature and cumulative CO₂ emissions that has been used to date can no longer be regarded as valid, at least from the year 2000 onwards. As a great number of forecasts for future developments (including the determination of CO₂ budgets in the IPCC AR6 report) as well as most emission reduction targets are based on this relationship, far-reaching changes must be made in these areas.

3.2 Assessment of the acceleration in the rate of temperature rise using the representative temperature function T_{cs}

Using the T_{cs} temperature function, it is possible to provide a clear answer to the question of whether the rate of temperature rise accelerated in 2023–2024, a topic that has been the subject of studies and discussions in recent months. As can be seen in Figure 9, the temperature values for 2023–2024 are distributed relatively evenly around the T_{cs} temperature function. The impression of an exceptional rise only arises when the inappropriate linear regression is used to analyse the temperature curve.

Since the temperature function T_{cs} is a parabolic function of time, a continuous increase in the rate of change is one of its natural properties. The rate of change is defined by the first derivative of the function (the tangent) and can be determined for any point. To illustrate this, the values for two decades are presented in Table 2 below. Two different methods of determination are given: the difference between the boundary values and the tangent at the midpoint of the interval. As can be seen, the two methods yield the same results.

<i>Period</i>	<i>Boundary values</i>	<i>Tangent</i>
2001-2010	0,17	0,17
2015-2024	0,40	0,40

Table 2 Increase in the mean GSAT temperature per decade in °C – calculated using the representative temperature function T_{cs} . Boundary values: temperature difference between the endpoints of the time interval. Tangent: tangent of the temperature function T_{cs} at the midpoint of the time interval.

Table 2 shows the extent to which the rate of temperature rise has accelerated and confirms the findings of studies that, using statistical methods, report similar values, such as Foster & Rahmstorf [1]. The increase rose to 0.4°C in the decade 2015–2025 (compared with 0.17°C in the decade 2001–2010). Currently (at the end of 2025), the increase is already 0.50°C per decade.

3.3 Determination of the time points at which important temperature thresholds are exceeded using the temperature function T_{cs}

The T_{cs} temperature function also enables more precise predictions of future trends. Until now, the timing of when the Paris Agreement targets of 1.5°C and 2°C will be exceeded has mostly been discussed in relation to the CO₂ budgets calculated in AR6 (see Figure 10).

Global Warming Between 1850–1900 and 2010–2019 (°C)		Historical Cumulative CO ₂ Emissions from 1850 to 2019 (GtCO ₂)					
1.07 (0.8–1.3; likely range)		2390 (± 240; likely range)					
Approximate global warming relative to 1850–1900 until temperature limit (°C) ^a	Additional global warming relative to 2010–2019 until temperature limit (°C)	Estimated remaining carbon budgets from the beginning of 2020 (GtCO ₂)					Variations in reductions in non-CO ₂ emissions ^c
		<i>Likelihood of limiting global warming to temperature limit^b</i>					
		17%	33%	50%	67%	83%	
1.5	0.43	900	650	500	400	300	Higher or lower reductions in accompanying non-CO ₂ emissions can increase or decrease the values on the left by 220 GtCO ₂ or more
1.7	0.63	1450	1050	850	700	550	
2.0	0.93	2300	1700	1350	1150	900	

Figure 10 Presentation of CO₂ budgets in AR6 [3] (Summary for Policymakers, Table SPM.2, p. 29)

For the calculation of CO₂ budgets, the AR6 used the linear relationship between cumulative CO₂ emissions and the rise in GSAT. However, as explained in this study, this relationship can no longer be regarded as valid, at least since the beginning of 2000. Figure 11 shows the dates on which the 1.5°C, 2°C and 3°C temperature thresholds are exceeded, using the T_{cs} temperature function and the 1.5°C and 2°C thresholds according to the AR6 CO₂ budget (67% probability of compliance). To determine the dates of exceedance, constant CO₂ emissions at the 2025 level (42.2 Gt CO₂) were assumed.

Figure 11 Timing of key temperature threshold crossings – comparison between the temperature function T_{cs} and the CO₂ budgets according to AR6 (67% probability of compliance, see Figure 10). Emissions data from the Global Carbon Budget 2025 (Friedlingstein et al., 2025, ESSD) were used to calculate the remaining budgets as of 1 January 2026.

Figure 11 illustrates the enormous differences in the timing of exceedances. It should be noted that, in the case of the T_{cs} temperature function, the final exceedance of the temperature threshold coincides with the point of intersection. The calculation of various exceedance probabilities, as in the case of CO₂ budgets, is not reasonable. As additional energy is constantly being added to the climate system, a return below the exceeded temperature threshold is only possible within the natural range of variation for individual monthly values over a limited period.

Calculations using T_{cs} show that the 1.5°C threshold was already exceeded in July 2025, whereas according to AR6, a remaining budget of approximately 150 Gt CO₂ should still be available from 1 January 2026, which – assuming emissions remain at 2025 levels – would not be exhausted until more than four years (July 2029).

According to the T_{cs} temperature function, the 2°C threshold will be exceeded as early as April 2034, whereas the AR6 GHG budget suggests this would not occur until 13 years later (April 2047). The 3°C threshold would be exceeded as early as mid-2047, i.e. just three months after the date forecast for 2°C in the AR6.

The massive acceleration in the rate of temperature rise identified in this study dramatically reduces the time available to implement measures designed to prevent temperature from rising to uncontrollable levels.

The use of the temperature function does not justify a meaningful definition of adjusted CO₂ budgets. The situation requires both the fastest possible decarbonisation as part of a global emergency plan and additional measures to increase albedo in order to stabilise the temperature.

3.4 Radiative forcing from self-reinforcing feedback loops becomes dominant

Another key finding is that the contribution of self-reinforcing cycles, which can be linked to the reduction in Earth's albedo, has become the dominant driver of temperature rise over the period under consideration (2000 to 2025), and particularly from 2010 onwards. At 2.38 W/m², it already exceeds the total anthropogenic CO₂ forcing since the start of the Industrial Revolution (approx. 2.28 W/m² by the end of 2025).

The reduction in Earth's albedo is primarily attributable to the decline in reflective low-level cloud cover, the retreat of Arctic ice and snow cover, and the melting of glaciers. An additional factor is the deterioration in the albedo of snow cover caused by soot particles from wildfires, as well as increased precipitation in the form of rain rather than snow. In most cases, these are self-reinforcing cycles. As already mentioned, the reduction in aerosol concentrations resulting from air pollution control measures in shipping and industry is also likely to contribute to this effect.

The albedo feedback effect has evidently been dramatically underestimated to date. The following values can be found in AR6 (see Figure 12):

Table 7.10 | Synthesis assessment of climate feedbacks (central estimate shown in bold). The mean values and their 90% ranges in CMIP5/6 models, derived using multiple radiative kernels (Zelinka et al., 2020) are also presented for comparison.

Feedback Parameter α_x (W m ⁻² °C ⁻¹)	CMIP5 GCMs	CMIP6 ESMs	AR6 Assessed Ranges			
	Mean and 5–95% Interval	Mean and 5–95% Interval	Central Estimate	Very likely Interval	Likely Interval	Level of Confidence
Planck	–3.20 [–3.3 to –3.1]	–3.22 [–3.3 to –3.1]	–3.22	–3.4 to –3.0	–3.3 to –3.1	<i>high</i>
WV+LR	1.24 [1.08 to 1.35]	1.25 [1.14 to 1.45]	1.30	1.1 to 1.5	1.2 to 1.4	<i>high</i>
Surface albedo	0.41 [0.25 to 0.56]	0.39 [0.26 to 0.53]	0.35	0.10 to 0.60	0.25 to 0.45	<i>medium</i>
Clouds	0.41 [–0.09 to 1.1]	0.49 [–0.08 to 1.1]	0.42	–0.10 to 0.94	0.12 to 0.72	<i>high</i>
Biogeophysical and non-CO ₂ biogeochemical	Not evaluated	Not evaluated	–0.01	–0.27 to 0.25	–0.16 to 0.14	<i>low</i>
Residual of kernel estimates	0.06 [–0.17 to 0.29]	0.05 [–0.18 to 0.28]				
Net (i.e., relevant for ECS)	–1.08 [–1.61 to –0.68]	–1.03 [–1.54 to –0.62]	–1.16	–1.81 to –0.51	–1.54 to –0.78	<i>medium</i>
Long-term ice-sheet feedbacks (millennial scale)				>0.0		<i>high</i>

Figure 12 Values of feedback parameters in AR6 [3] (Table 7.10, p. 978)

For surface albedo, the feedback parameter α (central estimate) is set at 0.32 (W m² °C⁻¹), and for clouds at 0.42. If the two parameters are combined as albedo feedback and converted to the temperature difference over the study period from 2000 to 2025, a ΔRF value of 0.565 W/m² is obtained.

The ΔRF value for albedo reduction determined in this study, at 2.38 W/m², is more than four times higher. The contribution of albedo feedback was therefore dramatically underestimated in AR6. This is, beside the already mentioned application of the linear relationship between the temperature rise and the cumulative CO₂ emissions, the second main cause of the large differences between the determined times of crossing important temperature thresholds in AR6 and the temperature function T_{cs} (see 3.3, Figure 11).

4. Conclusions and Discussion

The findings of this study are certainly alarming, as they indicate that the anthropogenic greenhouse effect is progressing at a significantly faster rate than previously assumed. The threat of exceeding the 2°C threshold in as little as eight years shows that humanity has only a few years left to act. After that, we would lose any possibility of taking action and would be moving unstopably towards critical tipping points that would trigger dramatic and irreversible developments.

Decarbonisation plans are based on the assumption of a linear relationship between cumulative emissions and the rise in average temperature and are therefore inadequate. Decarbonisation must be largely achieved within the next 10 years if there is to be any chance of stabilising the climate. The main target must be to halt the rise in temperature as quickly as possible, or at least to slow it down significantly.

Due to the rapidly increasing contribution of albedo feedback to global warming, decarbonisation alone is no longer sufficient to stabilise the climate at this stage. Measures to increase albedo must also be taken on at least the same scale.

At present, the self-reinforcing cycles responsible for the reduction in albedo are still reversible. This means that, if temperatures were to fall, they could have the opposite effect and support efforts to stabilise the climate. However, with a further rise in temperature, there is a risk of additional self-reinforcing cycles emerging that may no longer be reversible, such as the thawing of permafrost, which would release large quantities of CO₂ and CH₄ into the atmosphere.

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Appendix

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Conflict of Interest

The author declares no conflicts of interest relevant to this study.

Data availability statement

All data used in this study originates from publicly available sources:

The CERES-EBAF dataset is available from NASA at https://asdc.larc.nasa.gov/data/CERES/EBAF/TOA_Edition4.2/

ERA-5 reanalysis data are freely available in the Copernicus Climate Change Service Climate Data Store (<https://cds.climate.copernicus.eu/>)

Global CO₂ concentrations data are freely available from NOAA Global Monitoring Laboratory (<https://gml.noaa.gov/ccgg/trends/global.html>)

Data on the CO₂ emissions from Global Carbon Project can be downloaded at <https://www.icos-cp.eu/impact/science/global-carbon-budget/2025>